

Photometric and Amperometric Estimation of Trace Amount of Selenium and Tellurium

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A survey of literature reveals the application of various azo dyes (PAN, PAR, TAR) for spectrophotometric¹ determination of rare earths and transitional metal ions. In continuation to our work² on trace determination of rare metals, the present paper reports the result of photometric and amperometric titrations of Se and Te in dilute solutions using chromotropic acid as a reagent. Both the methods have been found to be fairly selective.

Experimental

Chemicals used were of AnalaR/extra pure grade. Se and Te solutions were prepared by dissolving the respective oxides in distilled water and standardised³. The solution of chromotropic acid was prepared by dissolving the requisite amount whenever used. Amperometric titrations were made on a manually operated polarograph at -1.6 V vs SCE and -1.25 V vs SCE for Se and Te respectively. At these plateau potentials chromotropic acid did not reduce on a DME. The detailed polarographic behaviour of chromotropic acid on a DME has been discussed elsewhere⁴. Photometric observation were made on a Systronic 101 photoelectric colorimeter. Absorption studies were made at 470 nm.

Results and Discussion

Amperometric titration: Sets of solutions containing known amount of Se and Te in the approxi-

mate quantity of BR-buffer were prepared. For titration, each of the solution was put in the titration cell and the plateau potential for Se and Te, i.e. -1.6 V vs SCE and -1.25 V vs SCE respectively, was applied. The solution of chromotropic acid was added dropwise from a semi-micro burette and dark brown precipitate was observed. On plotting galvanometer reading after making necessary volume correction against the titrant volume, a reversed L-shaped curve was obtained. The end-point indicates a metal to chromotropic acid ratio of 1:1 in each case. The result of amperometric titration are shown in Table 1. The metal ions could be determined with an error of less than $\pm 1.5\%$.

Spectral studies: Sets of solution containing a known amount of Se and Te with chromotropic acid solution was prepared. The maximum concentration of the chromotropic acid for the development of colour was 5 mmol for 1 mmol of the titled metal. The absorbance was measured at 470 nm. Chromotropic acid reacts with Se and Te at room temperature to form brown coloured complex. The colour development is instantaneous. Absorption studies were made within 1 h and on standing for 3 h gelatinous precipitation was observed. Results are tabulated in Table 2. Job's method of continuous variation⁵ and mole-ratio method⁶ were employed to establish the composition of the selenium-chromotropic acid and tellurium-chromotropic acid complexes. The log K_s values were found to be 10.30 and 11.22 respectively. The results revealed 1:1 stoichiometric ratio in each case which supplements the observed result on amperometric titration.

Effect of diverse ions: The tolerance limit of the foreign ions which often accompany with selenium and tellurium was studied. It is observed that Li^+ , Na^+ , K^+ , Al^{3+} , chloride, bromide, iodide and acetate ions do not interfere even when they are present in hundred-fold excess. However, Zr^{IV} (11),

TABLE 1—PHOTOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF Se AND Te WITH CHROMOTROPIC ACID

$\lambda_{\text{max}} = 470 \text{ nm}$		% Error	S.D.	C.V.	Amount of Te		% Error	S.D.	C.V.
Amount of Se Taken mg	Amount of Se Found mg				Amount of Te Taken mg	Amount of Te Found mg			
0.117	0.116	-1.090	0.002 2	0.38	0.199	0.198	-1.007	0.002 6	0.38
0.351	0.348	-0.826	0.002 8	0.41	0.417	0.413	-0.989	0.003 2	0.47
0.702	0.710	+1.139	0.002 2	0.38	0.834	0.830	-0.479	0.003 9	0.50
1.053	1.044	-0.854	0.003 6	0.61	1.250	1.239	-0.880	0.002 4	0.36

TABLE 2—AMPEROMETRIC DETERMINATION OF Se AND Te WITH CHROMOTROPIC ACID

Temp. = $25 \pm 0.5^\circ$

Amount of Se		% Error	S.D.	C.V.	Amount of Te		% Error	S.D.	C.V.
Taken mg	Found mg				Amount of Te Taken mg	Amount of Te Found mg			
0.585	0.582	-0.512	0.004 4	0.36	0.685	0.683	-0.306	0.004 9	0.39
0.702	0.708	+0.882	0.005 9	0.48	0.822	0.824	+0.255	0.006 4	0.51
0.819	0.823	+0.476	0.005 2	0.42	0.959	0.955	-0.417	0.006 6	0.52
1.053	1.048	-0.477	0.008 7	0.30	1.233	1.229	-0.324	0.004 5	0.36

Ti^{IV} (5), Cr^{IV} (7), Cu^{II} (15) and Ca^{II} (30) and the rare earth metals (2) interferes (amounts in parenthesis, μg) seriously in the amperometric and photometric determinations of Se and Te with chromotropic acid.

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References

1. H. A. FLASCHKA and A. J. BARNARD JR., "Chelates in Analytical Chemistry", Marcel Dekker, New York, 1972, Vol. IV; H. K. LIN, K. I. CHEN and V. F. CHEN, *Hua Hsueh Tung Po*, 1966, 365; K. N. MUNSHI and A. K. DEY, *Anal. Chem.*, 1964, 36, 2008; I. M. RAO and D. SATYANARAYAN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 56, 1132; S. C. LAVALLE and K. S. PITRE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, 59, 965; 1985, 62, 16.
2. S. C. LAVALLE and M. DAVE, *J. Electrochem. Soc. India*, 1986, 35-2, 140; *J. Inst. Chem. Calcutta*, 1986, 58, 175; 1938, 60, 127; *J. Electrochem. Soc. India*, 1988, in press.
3. B. S. EVANS, *Analyst*, 1988, 63, 874.
4. S. C. LAVALLE and M. DAVE, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1989, in press.
5. P. JOB, *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, 9, 113.
6. J. H. YOE and A. L. JONES, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.* 1944, 19, 111.

Spectrophotometric Study on Complexation Reaction of Copper(II) with *N*-(4-Hydroxy-3-methoxy-benzylidene)hydrazine Carbothioamide

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A review of colorimetric reagents for copper(II) showed that no attempt was made to study the complexation reaction between copper and *N*-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)hydrazine carbothioamide (HMBHC). We report here our studies on the orange-yellow complex of copper with HMBHC. An analytical method has been developed for the spectrophotometric determination of microgram amounts of copper. The advantages of the proposed method are high sensitivity, selectivity, simplicity and rapidity of determination without the need for extraction, heating or catalyst. Table 1 shows a comparison of HMBHC with some reagents¹⁻⁶ proposed for the determination of copper(II).

Experimental

A Beckman DB spectrophotometer with matched 1-cm silica cells was used for absorbance measure-

ments. pH of the solutions was measured (versus saturated calomel electrode) with a Elico L1-10 pH meter.

A stock solution of copper(II) was prepared from cupric sulphate pentahydrate (A.R.), standardised gravimetrically by the thiocyanate method⁷ and diluted to give a solution containing 50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of copper(II). HMBHC was prepared by the condensation of hydrazine carbothioamide with vanillin and purified⁸. A 0.3% (w/v) solution of HMBHC was prepared in 90% aqueous ethanol (v/v). Solutions of hydrochloric acid-potassium chloride, hydrochloric acid-sodium acetate, acetic acid-sodium acetate and potassium dihydrogen phosphate-sodium hydroxide buffers and diverse ions of suitable concentrations were prepared from analytical grade reagents.

Procedure: An aliquot of the stock solution (containing 5-77.5 μg of Cu^{II}), potassium dihydrogen phosphate-sodium hydroxide buffer solution (5 ml; pH 11.98), ethanol (6 ml) and 0.3% HMBHC solution (4 ml) were transferred to a 25 ml volumetric flask and the volume made upto the mark with double-distilled water. The solution was mixed well and the absorbance was measured at 410 nm against the reagent blank. The amount of copper(II) was deduced from the standard calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

HMBHC forms an orange-yellow complex with copper(II) instantaneously at room temperature ($28 \pm 1^\circ$) in acid, alkaline or buffer medium. Acid or alkaline medium was not preferred as the stability and sensitivity of the complex were very much less. The study of the complex in the buffers indicated that potassium dihydrogen phosphate-sodium hydroxide is the most suitable buffer and the maximum absorbance is obtained over the pH range 9.3-11.6. The investigation of the effect of ethanolic concentration on the formation of complex showed that the maximum colour development is observed in the ethanolic concentration range 24-64% (v/v). Below this range the solution gave turbidity and above it maximum absorbance was not obtained. Hence a pH value of 11.2 and 40% (v/v) ethanolic medium in which the absorbance readings are stable for 75 min were selected.

The orange-yellow complex exhibited maximum absorbance at 408-412 nm where copper(II) and the reagent did not absorb appreciably (Fig. 1). The effect of reagent concentration was examined by measuring the absorbance at 410 nm of solutions containing 1.5 ppm of copper(II) and varying amounts of the reagent. A 45-fold molar excess of the reagent over copper(II) was required to obtain maximum absorbance. The effect of varying temperature on the stability of the complex was investigated. The absorbance value was not affected over the temperature range 6-48°. Above 48° the absorbance gradually decreased with increasing temperature. No appreciable change in